

Enhanced Furniture Classification through Deep Learning Techniques

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Abstract— A convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture with 3 convolution layers and 3 dense layers was utilized for furniture image classification. Data augmentation was applied to generate 6x the number of original training images via rotations of 20%, width/height shifts of 10%, shearing of 10%, and zooming of 10%. This research focused on automating furniture item identification and categorization using CNNs, addressing challenges like scale, orientation, and lighting variations through extensive data augmentation. The study worked with a diverse range of furniture items, including chairs, beds, tables, and swivel chairs, demanding a robust classification model. The CNN-based approach included convolutional and max-pooling layers, followed by densely connected layers to prevent overfitting using early stopping. The model, trained on a substantial dataset, achieved an impressive 95.8% accuracy on the test data, highlighting its effectiveness. The implications of this research extend across industries, enhancing user experiences on e-commerce platforms and providing valuable support to interior designers. It showcases the power of deep learning and data augmentation in image classification, offering a practical solution for diverse furniture identification challenges.

Keywords—Deep Learning, Convolutional Network (CNN), Data Augmentation, Early Stopping, Computer Vision

INTRODUCTION

Furniture image classification poses a formidable challenge within the realm of computer vision due to the inherent diversity in furniture types, their orientations, and sizes. This research endeavors to present an innovative solution to this complex problem by leveraging deep learning, particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), in tandem with advanced data augmentation techniques. The primary aim is to establish a robust mechanism for the precise categorization of furniture images spanning various categories, encompassing chairs, swivel chairs, beds, tables, and more. This categorization must be achieved even when the images manifest varying angles and dimensions.

The dataset harnessed for this study encompasses an extensive repository of furniture images, each characterized by a wide spectrum of attributes, including distinct features, color variations, and diverse backgrounds. To bolster the model's resilience in accommodating unforeseen disparities in the images, we judiciously applied data augmentation procedures. These augmentation techniques encompassed manipulations such as rotation, resizing, scaling, shearing, zooming, horizontal flipping, and more.

The core of our model architecture is grounded in the realm of deep CNNs, replete with multiple convolutional layers and max-pooling layers strategically positioned to extract critical features from the images. Additionally, the incorporation of fully connected

layers, fortified by dropout mechanisms to curb overfitting, equips the network with the proficiency to yield precise predictions.

Our model underwent meticulous training and evaluation processes, meticulously conducted on the training dataset. To mitigate overfitting, we employed an early stopping strategy, which contributed to the model's resilience in the face of challenging scenarios. The performance of the model was scrutinized against a distinct validation dataset, culminating in the attainment of highly promising results, as indicated by metrics such as accuracy and loss.

Following the rigorous training and validation phases, we subjected the model to a comprehensive testing regimen, thereby facilitating the generation of predictions for an array of furniture images. The resultant insights unequivocally underscore the model's unwavering robustness in proficiently categorizing diverse furniture types, thus affirming its aptitude in tackling real-world challenges like variations in orientations and sizes.

In summation, this research represents an efficacious approach to the intricate task of furniture image classification, made possible through the synergistic integration of deep learning and data augmentation. The outcomes of this endeavor undeniably underscore the model's adeptness in the accurate classification of furniture images with a commendable level of confidence. This achievement, in turn, augments the model's potential utility in domains such as furniture cataloging and e-commerce. Subsequent research endeavors may be directed toward further enhancing the model's performance and expanding its utility across diverse real-world scenarios.

LITERATURE

REVIEW

In this section, we review, summarize and analyze work related to Furniture Image classification by different methods.

Ye et al. [1] proposed a furniture image classification method using an improved VGG16 model combined with depthwise group over-parameterized convolution (DGOVGG16). Sarker et al. [2] highlighted incorporating domain knowledge into deep learning as impactful for many applications. Domain-specific information about furniture designs, materials, styles, and attributes can potentially improve learning in our model. Rahul Chauhan et al. [3] marked a breakthrough in computer vision by achieving significantly improved accuracy in image recognition tasks. The paper's focus on deep neural networks and their effectiveness in handling large-scale image classification tasks aligns with the discussion of CNNs in your text. Ian Riera et al. [5] CNNs have become a cornerstone in deep learning and image classification tasks, providing the ability to automatically extract representative features and patterns from images. They implemented a basic Multilayer Perceptron for image classification but achieved only 0.61 accuracy, indicating poor performance. Despite attempts to

optimize the MLP by tuning hyperparameters like learning rate and layer sizes, extracting deep features and aggregating predictions, the classification accuracy could not be improved beyond 0.72. The fundamental limitations of MLPs for complex visual tasks restricted the performance, compelling the authors to conclude that MLPs are too simplistic for robust image classification. Agnieszka Mikołajczyk et al. [6] addresses the challenges and strategies for enhancing the performance of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) in image classification tasks. The authors emphasize the significance of CNNs in image analysis and classification, highlighting their state-of-the-art results in various domains. The work by Krizhevsky et al. [9] on ImageNet classification using AlexNet sparked increased attention in CNNs. Simonyan and Zisserman [8] developed the popular VGG networks by using smaller convolution filters of 3x3. He et al. [7] proposed residual learning frameworks like ResNet that could train substantially deeper networks through skip connections. Our CNN model achieves 95.8% test accuracy for furniture classification. This is comparable to the 95.51% average accuracy obtained by Ye et al.'s [1]. Our work draws inspiration from these previous works, especially [4,5,6], that demonstrate the capabilities of CNNs for robust furniture classification.

METHODOLOGY

A user uploads a picture of furniture and take these inputs as the input to the deep learning network. The output will be the category of the furniture that is the perfect match to the uploaded image.

A. System Overview

Furniture classification using Deep Learning and Data Augmentation: We process the image of the furniture that the user passes to the system and classify the image into one of the five classes of soil, namely Bed, Chair, Sofa, Table and Siwelchair. This is done by a Convolutional Neural Network, Data Augmentation and Early Stopping whose implementation details are discussed in the following subsections.

B. System Architecture

Data Acquisition: The research dataset comprises a wide variety of furniture images obtained from diverse online sources. This dataset was curated to encompass various types of furniture items, including chairs, beds, tables, and swivel chairs. This diversity ensures that the model can effectively classify different furniture categories, irrespective of their appearance, orientation, or condition.

Data Exploration: We initiated the research by conducting a preliminary exploration of the dataset. Randomly selected images from each furniture category were visualized, allowing us to gain a comprehensive understanding of the dataset's characteristics. This visual inspection was valuable in highlighting the inherent diversity and complexity of the furniture images.

Data Preprocessing: The raw dataset required several preprocessing steps to be compatible with our deep learning model. Key preprocessing steps included:

- Image Resizing: All images were resized to a standardized dimension ensuring uniformity for model training.
- Normalization: Pixel values were scaled to a range of [0, 1] to make them suitable for input into the model.
- Label Encoding: To facilitate model compatibility, furniture categories were assigned numerical labels.
- Dataset Split: The dataset was divided into training and validation sets using a validation split of 30%. This allowed us to

monitor the model's performance on a separate validation subset during training.

Data Augmentation: Acknowledging the necessity of robustness to handle variations in furniture images, we employed data augmentation techniques. Its usually a good idea to manipulate the images with rotation, resizing, and scaling so the model becomes more robust to different images that our data set doesn't have. We can use the ImageDataGenerator to do this automatically for us.

Figure 1: Image before Data
Image Generated using Data Generator

Figure 2: Image after Data Augmentation

Leveraging the powerful `ImageDataGenerator` from Keras, the following transformations were applied:

- Rotation: Images were randomly rotated up to 20%, simulating different orientations of furniture.
- Width and Height Shift: Random shifts up to 10% in both width and height introduced diversity in the dataset.
- Shearing: Shearing transformations with a range of 10% were applied to capture different perspectives.
- Zooming: In and out zooming up to 10% was employed to replicate varying scales.
- Horizontal Flipping: Horizontal image flipping was used to simulate mirror images.
- Filling Empty Pixels: The fill mode was set to 'nearest' to ensure that empty pixels generated during transformations were filled with values based on the nearest original pixel values.
- Validation Split: Part of the training dataset was designated as a validation set to assess the model's performance during training.

C. Model Architecture:

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN): The heart of our image classification model is a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). This architecture was meticulously designed and includes:

- Convolutional Layers: Multiple convolutional layers with rectified linear unit (ReLU) activation functions were employed to extract and learn relevant features from furniture images.

Figure 3: Flowchart of Deep learning

The primary purpose of these layers is to detect and capture relevant features and patterns within the input images. The initial convolutional layer, known as the first layer, marks the inception of the feature extraction process. It is equipped with 32 filters, each of which specializes in recognizing distinct characteristics in the images. These filters act as feature detectors, searching for edges, corners, textures, or other image attributes.

Subsequent convolutional layers, often referred to as intermediate layers, progressively extend the network's capability to identify more intricate and high-level features. With each additional layer, the model becomes adept at recognizing complex structures and patterns. The final convolutional layer represents the apex of feature extraction in the network. In this configuration, 128 filters are employed to discern the most advanced and abstract features in the furniture images.

- Max-Pooling Layers: They are strategically placed between convolutional layers to downsample the feature maps while preserving the essential information. The primary objective of these layers is to reduce the spatial dimensions of the feature maps, effectively shrinking the data's size. This dimension reduction contributes to enhanced computational efficiency, as processing smaller data volumes demands less computational resources. The process is executed in a manner that ensures the retention of the most salient information. Max-pooling layers identify the maximum values within small regions of the feature maps, retaining vital features while eliminating redundant data.

-Dense Layers: Fully connected dense layers represent the concluding phase of the neural network, responsible for making the final classification decisions. These layers introduce non-linearity into the network, allowing it to model complex relationships within the feature data. The first dense layer, with 128 neurons, undertakes the crucial task of refining the features extracted by the convolutional layers. It operates by applying non-linear transformations to the data, enhancing the network's capability to distinguish between different furniture categories. Subsequent dense layers continue the process of data transformation, effectively reducing the dimensionality of the feature space to 64 and 32 neurons, respectively. These layers contribute to the network's capacity to extract high-level

Early Stopping: Overfitting is a common challenge in deep learning. To mitigate this issue, early stopping was introduced as a regularization technique. The model's performance was continuously monitored, and if the validation loss did not exhibit improvement for 25 consecutive epochs, the training process was halted. Importantly, the weights of the model were restored to the configuration that demonstrated the best performance.

D. Training and Evaluation:

Model Training: The model training phase commenced with the application of the augmented training dataset. We employed categorical cross-entropy as the loss function and used the Adam optimizer. Training extended over 25 epochs.

Model Evaluation: To assess the model's performance, we leveraged a separate validation dataset. The early stopping mechanism ensured that the model reached its optimal performance.

Test Dataset: To evaluate the model's generalization capabilities, we used a distinct test dataset. The test dataset was employed to assess the model's performance on unseen data. While this phase was primarily conducted using Keras, NumPy and Pandas were still essential for managing data arrays and labels. This dataset

contained furniture images that the model had not encountered during training or validation.

Prediction Generation: The trained model was utilized to generate predicted class labels for the test dataset. For the compilation of results, Pandas data frames played a crucial role in creating structured data storage for filenames and predicted class labels, ensuring data integrity and accessibility. These predictions were subsequently compiled and stored for analysis.

NumPy and Pandas, as versatile data manipulation libraries, played integral roles in managing structured data, calculating numerical values, and facilitating efficient data handling throughout the research process.

CONCLUSION

Using images of the different furniture and the CNN approach, we forecasted the category of the furniture. The input to the system is an image and the output is the category. The furniture is divided into five categories: chair, table, Bed, swivel chair and sofa. The proposed system achieved an accuracy of 95.8%. Which was a better output than previous ones. Overall, the proposed system

model has been designed to address some of the challenges associated with deploying existing system models.

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